

ISSUES OF HEALTH PROTECTION AND SAFETY OF LIFE ACTIVITIES IN THE STUDY OF THE LEXICAL TOPIC "PERSONALITY AND PROFESSION"

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Abstract: Their ways are often misinterpreted, both collectively and individually. From years of observation, these mishaps are primarily due to the lack of understanding and resources available to investigate such issues, especially in masses. Team effectiveness and efficiency depend on numerous factors, such as structure, competencies of team members, commitment, collaboration, support, benchmarks of perfection, and leadership qualities. It is the most important component; the individuals can benefit from an evaluation of how each of their unique characteristics can contribute to the whole. Thus, we investigate the personality type and see if it has an association with their ethnicity, as well as correlations to their individual team roles.

Keywords: Issues of health protection, specific technology, the individuals can benefit. In each case, the work is based on a specific technology. This will help make that work perfect and of good quality. Nowadays, every industry has its own technology. In this regard, the use of innovative technologies in the formation of pronunciation skills of children with hearing impairment is expected to be very effective. The effectiveness of innovative technology depends on its careful design. We know that on the basis of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2016 "On measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 2017-2021" the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017 Resolution No. 19 of 19 July "On Improving the Activities of Preschool Educational Institutions" contains a hearing on the Regulation "On a specialized state preschool educational institution for children with physical or mental disabilities." It is necessary to bring up children in accordance with their cognitive abilities, to correct their shortcomings, to prepare them for school education according to their abilities, to help them adapt to society. The beginning is of particular importance. Today in our country a lot of attention is paid to innovative technologies. Carrying out a lot of work on the introduction of education based on innovative technologies in the education of children with hearing impairments, the creation of various programs for them, ICT-based training transition, to create lesson plans suitable for contemporary students.

As companies strive to save costs in every department possible, they have realized that investing in their human resources and its process is just as important as investing in any other domain in their business. Online questionnaires are not reliable data collection. Psychologists have long emphasized that determining one's personality traits using these questionnaires can help determine how well they do in a given task. Based on these recommendations, many personality-type questionnaires have been developed, some with little to no credibility. Therefore, one must be careful upon making the decision of which one

to use. The great works of psychologist Geert Hofstede, and how he was able to identify cultural groups into clusters of 'types', were of great interest as in Kuwait's Food and Beverage Sector; there are many stereotypes and unexplained happenings when it comes to imported laborers. There are obvious qualities that were noticed over the years, but most remained simply stereotypes without much further explanation.

Perhaps there was a scientific way of answering questions like why one type of ethnicity does better at a certain job or task than another. In this work, which aims to find a connection between ethnicity, personality type, and team roles, Hofstede's findings will be used as a starting point to explore and investigate any connections as used in other scientific works. To build a well-balanced team, the diversity in team roles and skills has been seen as an important factor, therefore, the present study examines the ethnicity factor and its influence on the team roles. Furthermore, the need for flexibility and higher performance has increased with the continuously changing environment. The productivity level of an organisation is dependent upon the team performance and the role played by each member of the team. Moreover, team performance had been seen as an effective methodology to deal with the challenges. Teams are the crucial element of the organization, which can ensure high-performance within an organization. In current scenarios, team performance and work have gained widespread recognition to accomplish the organizational goals. In effect, the need to recognize the efforts in the team has increased over the past few decades. Team effectiveness and efficiency depend on numerous factors that can range from structure, competencies of team members, commitment, collaboration, support, benchmarks of perfection, and leadership qualities. In the present paper, the central focus is Belbin's theory of teamwork. It has been seen as one of the highly relevant theories which are scientifically tested and evaluated by researchers. The study will examine the correlations between ethnicity & personality types, as well as how they relate to team roles. It is significant as it will help determine the right person for the right job in terms of ethnicity, personality, and expected team role. The correct choice of personality will ensure that the specific team role is performed by the person chosen. Furthermore, the study explores the relationship between personality traits and team roles associated with a specific ethnicity. The paper proposes that personality traits and ethnicity have an impact on bringing out the team role, and therefore suggests a new technique through which organisations can plan to construct an effective team. The study will add to the existing literature pertaining to personality, team role and ethnicity from an unexplored angle in past literature.

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